

Luanda Leaks – A Conceptual Approach

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Forewords

The international Media in the last days is giving news about a possible appropriation of money belonging to Angola State in advantage of a misconduct of the PR of Angola, favouring a familiar.

I believe necessary to make a framework of the conceptual definitions about the facts announced by the media in order to make an opinion about what it is transmitted by TV's to the public..

Money laundering

Money laundering is presented as an activity that is, carrying out acts concatenated in time and space, with a view to achieving a determined goal. Those linked actions are concealment, concealment and integration.

From the point of view of the strategic action of organized crime, concealment and concealment are antecedent movements to integration action, when "dirty money" re-enters the economy in the form of lawful market investments.

At that stage, it will rarely be possible to recover the assets generated by the illegal activities. In a context of worsening socio-economic conditions in countries classified as "emerging", on all continents, there are three vectors that can be highlighted:

- a) The fall in profitability of traditional businesses, a world in which products are produced and services are provided, the so-called real economy;
- b) The increase in poverty, on a world scale, with the increasing deconstruction of the world of work;
- c) The lack of control over Financial Markets and capital flows by States and multilateral organizations such as the World Bank (IBRD), the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Trade Organization (WTO), as well as multilateral organizations linked to the United Nations (UN).

There is a huge negative impact that huge flows of illicit money can have on the financial sector.

It is in this context that the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision and Regulation stated that:

Public confidence in banks and, therefore, their stability, may be undermined by adverse publicity as a result of banks' inadvertent association with criminals.

In addition, banks can expose themselves to direct losses due to fraud, either through negligence in screening unwanted customers or when the integrity of their own employees has been compromised by association with criminals.

In facing the above problems, the affected countries can do little for themselves. This is mainly due to the international nature of money laundering.

For example, it was observed that:

The laundering of the proceeds of crime is indeed an international phenomenon. Operations are no longer limited to the country in which the illicit money is generated. On the contrary, the cross-border movement of money is now a prominent feature of laundering operations. Evidence from around the world supports this view.

For example, Rodriguez Gacha is estimated to have laundered \$ 130 million in funds from the Medellín Cartel, using 82 company and other accounts in 16 countries. In addition, in the "Polar Cap" case, \$ 1.2 billion in cocaine money is believed to have been laundered for the Medellín Cartel through a complicated system of fake gold and jewelry deals in the United States. The funds were deposited in the United States, then transferred to Panama and from there to accounts in Europe and South America.⁸ In addition, a recent analysis of the Canadian police money laundering archives revealed that more than 80% had a size international.

The obvious way out, therefore, was through international cooperation.

Multilateral money laundering agreements have existed, at least since the early 20th century. In 1972 to 2000, no fewer than 12 multilateral drug control treaties were concluded.

Efforts were then mainly directed towards regulating the supply and movement of medicines, with the aim of limiting their manufacture and import to the quantities necessary for legitimate medical and scientific purposes.

In 1988, with the adoption of the United Nations Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (Vienna Convention), there was a fundamental change in the approach.

This agreement places great emphasis on tracking the illicit wealth of money launderers. This approach is generally advocated for the following reasons:

(1) To the extent that criminals act in the same way as money, the best deterrent and punishment is to confiscate their incentives;

(2) While the highest and most powerful criminals rarely come into contact with illicit goods, such as drugs, from which they make their profits, they come into contact with the proceeds from the sale of those goods. This contact usually provides a "paper trail" or other evidence, which is the only connection to a violation of the law and;

(3) Confiscating the proceeds of criminal activities is a good way to make law enforcement pay.

Article 3 of the Vienna Convention requires countries, among other things, to establish as criminal offenses under their national legislation, activities such as the production, manufacture, distribution or sale of illicit drugs and the organization, administration or financing of illicit trafficking, when committed intentionally; the conversion or transfer of ownership, knowing that that ownership is derived from any of the above offenses; the concealment or disguise of true nature

Money Laundering and Corruption

Although it is defined as "the misuse of public power for private benefit", corruption can also be described as representing disagreement with the "familiarity" principle (arm's-length), which mandates that no personal or family relationship should play any role in economic decision-making, whether operated by private economic agents or government officials.

The principle of familiarity is seen as fundamental to the efficient functioning of any organization

A relevant definition establishes corruption as a transaction between actors in the public and private sectors, where collective assets are illegitimately converted into private gains (Heidenheimer et al, 1989: 6, cited by Andvig et al, 2000).

This point is emphasized by Rose-Ackerman, who says that corruption exists at the interface between the public and private sectors (Rose-Ackerman, 2000).

Colin Nye's classic definition establishes corruption as "behavior that deviates from the formal duties of a public role (elected or appointed) motivated by private gains (personal, family, etc.) in wealth or status" (Nye 1967: 416, quoted by Andvig et al, 2000).

Nye's concept of corruption is, as it turns out, a concept centred on the civil service. Heywood says that the fact that the concept focuses only on the public sphere allows it to only cover the practices of corruption that occur within that sphere or at the interface between the public and private spheres; which means that other practices that occur within the private sphere are left out, such as financial corruption.

Klitgaard (1998) is another of the authors who considers corruption as a form of misuse of public office for private benefits or for unofficial purposes. He developed a formula by which corruption can be defined. The formula is as follows:

$$C = M + D - A$$

Where: C = Corruption; M = Monopoly; D = Discretionary; A = Accountability

For Klitgaard, whether it is a public or private activity, or a non-profit activity, whether it happens in Bamako or Washington, corrupt practices can be found when an organization or a person has a monopoly of power over a good or certain services, has the discretion to decide who will receive it and in what quantities, but no accountability rules or practices.

For Klitgaard, in a similar context, there is more space for the occurrence of corrupt practices, which can only be controlled if the monopoly is reduced, the discretion clarified and the transparency increased, together with an increase in formal disincentives (costs) / cool. Like the classic concept of Nye, the concept proposed by Klitgaard is also too legalistic, not following social values and behaviours.

Inspired by this Principal-Agent model, Della Porta and Vanucci (2005) define political and bureaucratic corruption as:

- (i) A hidden breach of the contract that, implicitly or explicitly, establishes the delegation of responsibilities and some exercise of discretionary power;
- (ii) By a public Agent who, against the Principal's preferences or interest (his public organization), acts on behalf of a third party from whom he receives a bribe.

Thus, according to the authors, the "contracts" that the Agents establish with the State - and in this sense with the citizens that the State represents - impose the respect of the rules that restrict the Agent's discretionary power, precisely to limit the potential for conflict between the Agent's private interests and the Principal's interests.

In this perspective, there will be corruption if the Public Agent does not respect the rules because of the intervention of a third party, the corruptor; this intervention induces the Agent to sell the resources related to his role (be it decision-making power, reserved information or protection, in order to obtain an advantage).

The Principal-Agent model

The Principal-Agent model is one of the theoretical frameworks commonly used to analyze problems related to corruption. It is a situation in which an Agent serves - or fails to serve - the Principal's interest. The Agent is the person who accepts an obligation to act on behalf of his Principal and, in doing so, serves his Principal's

interests as if they were his own. The Principal can be a natural person or a legal entity (organization or even the general public).

When acting on behalf of the Principal, an Agent will have to exercise some discretion; and the greater the range of subjects (measured in terms of effects on the Principal's interests) that he can exercise, his discretion increases.

According to Banfield, the situation includes third parties, abstract persons or entities, which may gain or lose due to the agent's action. But in this relationship there are rules (laws and other social norms) whose violation contains the probability of penalty (Costs) that is imposed on the violator.

In some cases, these rules may be more or less ambiguous or vague and sometimes there is no certainty that they can be applied.

Banfield also describes situations where an Agent is corrupt. An Agent is personally corrupt when he sacrifices the Principal's interests for his benefit, undermining the existing trust; an Agent is officially corrupt if, serving the Principal's interest, he knowingly violates the rules, acting illegally and outside ethical standards, harming his Principal's interests.

The question of Costs incurred by the Agent is related to the levels of dependence that mark the relations between the two entities.

1. Agents are dependent to varying degrees; but the more independent they are, the greater the Costs that can result from an act of corruption. The notion of costs that Banfield exposes should be seen as meaning a disincentive

2. Agents receive a set of incentives that will motivate them to obey and be loyal to the Principal; but there is also a set of disincentives in case of disobedience, such as the risk of job loss or pension rights; these risks are disincentive to disobedience.

According to Banfield, this type of relationship requires centralized control, with an authority capable of selecting dependent agents, establishing a clear incentive system, explaining the Principal's interests to the Agent and monitoring the monitors

3. Based on this model, anti-corruption policies can be designed with a focus on the preventive and repressive approach. Preventive through the restoration of incentives and repressive through the restoration of disincentives in case of disobedience (which include criminal costs).

Black, gray and white corruption

In order to avoid what Speck et al call "culturalist bias", Heidenheimer (1970) suggested a line of investigation based on the concept of corruption by the social

actors themselves. Based on an inductive definition, the author suggested three categories of corruption:

- Black corruption: when the law and social coincide
- Gray corruption: when the actors assess certain behaviours in a controversial way
- White corruption: when the law disapproves, but the majority of the population is tolerant (Heidenheimer, quoted by Speck et al).

A more recent version but containing the same elements was proposed by Mushtaq Khan, who says that corruption is "a behaviour that deviates from the formal rules of conduct, of someone with a position of public authority, because of private reasons such as wealth, power, status "(Khan, 1997).

Conflict of interests – Public and Private – National - International

Interests are tangible things, such as land, money, or jobs that can be traded and compromised, while needs are intangible things, such as identity, security, and recognition that are not for trading.

Since needs are intangible, they are often hidden underneath the more visible conflict over interests.

What defines the "extent possible" in this largely procedural conceptualization is an existing distribution of values (wealth, power, prestige, etc.) that is generally taken as given or as changeable, if at all, only by processes other than conflict resolution.

This flows from the initial premise that the parties in conflict share common social norms.

An actual conflict of interests exists when a reasonable person, in possession of the relevant facts, would conclude that the official's private interests are likely to interfere with the proper performance of their official duties. For example, the use of knowledge gained in the course of official duties to obtain a lucrative consultancy.

Corruption and Power

The possibility of corruption is part of the nature of power. Whoever has power has the ability to modify the structure of property rights, additionally in exchange for goods.

The State is the privileged means of modifying property rights; it can expropriate or it can “collect” financial or material instruments through taxes; it also has the power to give special treatment to some citizens, arbitrarily applying legislation, especially taxation; it can grant or revoke licenses or credits to trade in the country or abroad or to use the territory.

The most paradigmatic case is the award of public works contracts. For these reasons, corruption primarily concerns the public sector.

State corruption is a problem of the legality of power, not of morality. It is an illegal behaviour of those who play a role in the state apparatus.

Corruption violates fundamental rights, limits freedom and distorts a state's economy, bringing with it unfair choices, as well as the poverty of those not benefiting from embezzlement.

For these reasons it must be combated. In the discussion of policies to combat corruption, two main lines of action emerge: measures to prevent it and actions to repress the corrupt.

These actions are not mutually exclusive; on the contrary, new measures of both types must be created, developing prevention and tightly sealing the application of repression.

The World Bank distinguishes between “administrative corruption” and “capture of the state”

(1) Administrative corruption refers to distortions or impositions in the implementation of existing laws or regulations to provide advantages to state or private agents in exchange for illegal benefits. It is an individualized exception to its application.

(2) The state is "captured" when it regulates in the interests of private interests, as opposed to the public interest.

Not only can the private sector be corrupting, but the State itself, when it promotes or grants in some way certain people, employees or individuals, to certain positions or honours, in exchange for favours and services provided.

As the biggest problem in politics, corruption is, unfortunately, dealt mainly with its punctual and repressive moral aspect

Corruption affects politics in at least three dimensions.

- The first is the existence of small favours, available to be distributed by politicians;

- The second is the ability of financial groups to obtain these benefits illegally;
- The third is the temporal instability of political alliances.

Conclusion

In the media noticed hypothesis we have an international organized crime.

Indeed the operational development of the related facts have the inherent common denominators THE STRUCTURE, SAFETY and FINANCING of the criminal organizations (banks, communications, real state and industrial units..

Still in relationship to a large part of the organized crime (except partly, the terrorist organizations), we can find another common element: the type of Operational Development.

The Operational Development of the activities of organized criminality settles down, usually, according to the following vectors:

- a) Extent of national, international and transnational action;
- b) Permanent Operational and stabilized, with concerns of tactics and of strategic order;
- c) Conjugation of legal businesses and illicit businesses;
- d) Chronological Interface and multiple accomplishments of crimes.

The operational development of the organized criminality has these factors.

a) - the reason of being of this criminality type is inside the enlarged extent of territorial activity and permanent organization and stabilized in the prosecution of the criminal activities;

b) - the reason of effectiveness of the organizations, for besides the execution of their objectives (namely, the economical profits), is into in their flexibility face the deterrent circumstances, in dynamics of tactical and strategic articulation in the capacity of dissimulation of the illicit financing sources (illicit businesses), through the creation and maintenance of licit businesses (real or simulated) that, allow to justify and to "clean" the obtained global profits.

At the level of the businesses illicit/crimes, are strategies those that, best allows the "normal" prosecution of the activities of financing of the organization. The practices of the corruption, covering, and traffic of influences and control of the authorities are usual and typical.

The organization strategically to mislead difficulties and to avoid (larger) threats to the operational development of the activities chose as tactics for the organization to obtain profit, by e.g. traffic of diamonds, smuggling, among others.

The legal businesses more "sought" by the criminal organization are spread in several sectors, as: the finance market (e.g. detention and/or participation in credit institutions, leasing societies, brokers.) and the market of capitals - preferred by excellence for practices of bulky operations of money laundry -, the building societies and other businesslike import - export firms (often based in taxes paradises - off - shores).

Actually, the infiltration of the organized crime in legal businesses constitutes an additional tactic for effective reduction of the risk of detection of the net, for the covering and legitimating the incomes produced that, like this, less suspicions get up as for its ownership. Still, the insert in activities and legitimate commercial operations, namely at the international level, offers to the criminal organizations the possibility to use the legal circulation and transport of products for part of their illicit cargo.

c) - The criminological reason of the organized crime is partially, in the multiple accomplishment of illicit and, the criminal interaction.

The operational development of the net give priority to the practice of multiple illicit criminal be in the optical of safety expressed in:

- Crimes of corruption;
- Traffic of you influence;
- Threats;
- Drainage of incomes;
- Crime of money laundry;
- Falsifications;
- Tax frauds.

The international criminal authorities are aware of these facts and sure that the media did its mission about denouncing not only a criminal organization but also protecting the Angola democracy, in the case that the Court of Justice believes in the evidences and condemn all the members of the organization by internal and international Law.

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